

LIVED EXPERIENCES AND CHALLENGES OF FARMERS AFFECTING PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING: BASIS FOR AN EXTENSION PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

The study explored the lived experiences of farmers in Barangay Pal-ew, Tanjay City, focusing on the challenges affecting their psychological health. Using a qualitative design based on Heideggerian phenomenology, the research sought to understand the farmers' lived and existential experiences. A total of twenty-five (25) small-scale farmers with land areas of less than 1 acre participated, with the majority being male (64%) and female (36%). Most participants fell within the 41–50 age group (32%), while the least represented were those aged 21–30 (8%). Participants were given open-ended survey questionnaires to elicit deep, narrative accounts of their experiences. The findings revealed several factors impacting their psychological well-being, including unpredictable weather conditions, limited access to fertilizers due to financial constraints, insufficient farming equipment and resources, and lack of knowledge. Climate change emerged as a significant factor contributing to poor farming productivity, with unpredictable weather negatively affecting crop growth. Addressing these challenges, comprehensive psychological and agricultural extension programs are essential, as they provide farmers with the training, resources, and guidance needed to improve their knowledge and adapt to modern and sustainable practices.

Keywords: *Heideggeran phenomenology, lived experiences, psychological well-being*

INTRODUCTION

Farmers play a significant role in the global sector, being considered the backbone of the food industry. The Asia-Pacific Region which the Philippines belongs, accounts for 60 percent of the world's population, with 70 percent of that population belonging to farming families. Small-scale food producers such as farmers, fisherfolks, herders, and others contribute to 80 percent of the region's food supply (FAO, n.d.). Collectively, their primary role is indispensable as the prime movers of ensuring global food security, cultivating crops and providing essential nutrition to the world's population. Farmers contributed to a larger economic force, being the source of livelihood of millions and sustenance for a significant portion of people in rural areas.

In the Philippines, farmers typically cultivate 1 hectare or less, or between 1-3 hectares, which accounts for 32% of the total 7.2 million hectares of agricultural land. (World Bank, 2021). A dominant portion of farming sector consists of small-scale farmers who are burdened with numerous challenges such as poor access to resources, low income, and even impact of climate change. Additionally, Oakeshott (2018), further elaborated on these challenges, noting limited opportunities for improvement due to difficulty in acquiring financial support, small farm sizes, and lack of agricultural knowledge. While they present a significant portion of the population, these farmers also face issues that negatively affect their psychological well-being.

Daghagh (2019), further exemplifies that farmers face unique physical and psychological challenges often characterized by long hours demanding physical work, income uncertainty, and at times social isolation. Wheeler et. al, (2023), pointed out that adding to the stress level of farmers are unpredictable weather patterns, shifting agricultural policies, and unstable market conditions. All these factors have significantly impacted the psychological well-being of farmers. A direct focus on these issues can help better understand and support the needs of the farming community.

Beginning with, climate change, as it presents threat to the agriculture sector which is highly vulnerable due to its heavy reliance on rainfall that is also susceptible to typhoons, droughts, and other extreme weather condition. This hazardous change in the climate significantly impacted the agricultural status of the country leading to increased risks to food security, economic losses, and reduced crop production. The International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI) & Philippine Institute for Development Studies, have highlighted the adverse effect of climate change on yielded crops. Among these impacts are rising global commodity prices and reduced food consumption. By 2030 and 2050, agricultural food commodity is projected to continue increasing making food commodities less accessible particularly for the poor people. Additionally, the greatest impact is the challenge to food security, which may result to higher rates of childhood malnutrition and greater number of people experiencing hunger.

The rapid destruction of climate change, bringing less earnings and less sufficiency to sustain their livelihoods which hampers their psychological well-being. The country's poverty incidence rate of 30% in 2021, farmers still remain the poorest in the nation (Ramos, 2023). Moreover, Ocampo (2024) emphasized that according to the Department

of Budget and Management, the agricultural sector accounted for 9.1 % to Philippines' gross domestic product in 2023 which does not equate with the economic status of the farmers. They considered as the country's lifeblood, but, are faced with challenge in securing financial help.

According to the Banko Sentral ng Pilipinas 2021 Financial Inclusion Survey, farmers or workers in the agricultural sector had the highest exclusion level, with 73 percent having no accounts. In addition, Skalon, et. al (2024), point out the various challenges in providing agricultural insurance. In the Philippines, the provision of agricultural insurance remains limited, according to a World Bank study. The challenges contributing to this situation include the unsuitability of insurance services for most farmers, critical operations faced by the Philippine Crop Insurance Corporation, poorly targeted government subsidies (Ocampo, 2024).

Another growing concern for Filipino farmers are lack of agricultural knowledge and information. Reitz (2006), emphasized that rural areas have limited access to agricultural information; Odini (2014), intensifies that insufficient information, poor agricultural systems, and illiteracy have contributed lack awareness to rural areas. Farmers live in rural areas as their mainstay, and even have knowledge gap with agricultural information services WorldBank, 2000). Agricultural information awareness has been a challenge to the farmers (Shetto, 2008); information services increase gap of awareness resulting to poor information (Aker, 2010).

Farmers have inevitably been facing those problems that negatively affected their psychological well-being, Rivas (2020), affirmed that Filipino farmers have been challenged mentally, emotionally, and financially. Fraser et. Al (2005), emphasized that farmers are prone to a range of physical and mental health issues due to difficult working conditions. These circumstances have contributed to chronic stress, which significantly influences their overall well-being and health. Stress has ever been linked to the prevalence of mental disorders such as depression and anxiety (McShane, et. al 2016). Oftentimes, the demands of their work are overwhelming, that it become difficult to manage, control, and cope with, ultimately resulting in work-related stress. (Lunner, et. al., 2025).

Ultimately, these conditions have influenced the psychological well-being of the farmers, often leaving them exhausted and less productive at work. Therefore, the researchers have undertaken this study to understand the wide array of challenges they face, including their lived experiences that affect their psychological well-being, and to develop programs that can address and mitigate these issues.

Research Questions

The study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the different experiences of farmers that affected their psychological well-being?
2. What are the leading factors that contributed to stress among farmers?

3. What are the different challenges faced by the farmers?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a qualitative design using Heideggerian phenomenology, an interpretive method concerned with understanding lived and existential experiences, positioning individuals as fundamentally *being-in-the-world* within their embodied contexts. (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Heidegger, 1962; Smythe et al., 2008). The researchers identified this as the most suitable methodology for the study on understanding the lived experiences of farmers dealing with challenges that affected their psychological well-being.

The research locale is Barangay Pal-ew, Tanjay City, Negros Oriental. The total population of the barangay is 5,125, according to the 2020 Census which accounts for 6.20% of the total population of the city. The 1,078 households are reported to have an average of 4.62 members based on the 2015 Census. The location is approximately 9.5146, 123.0298, on the island of Negros. The elevation at these coordinates is estimated at 367.3 meters or 1,205.0 feet above mean sea level (PhilAtlas, n.d.). The barangay is in a hilly hinterland that forms parts of its mountainous terrain, with farming serving as the primary source of livelihood.

The demographics of the respondents range from 21 to 76 years of age and include both male and female farmers. Participants were selected through purposive sampling, resulting in a total of 36 farmers. Etikan, et. al (2016) describe this type of sampling as the deliberate selection of participants with specific characteristics, experiences, or knowledge relevant to the study.

The participants were fully informed about the confidentiality of their responses. Participation was voluntary, and they could withdraw at any time without any negative consequences. The Data Privacy Act was also strictly observed, along with other ethical considerations, which were diligently followed.

The participants were handed with survey questionnaires composed of open-ended questions designed to elicit deep, and narrative accounts of their lived experiences. Deakin University (2016) also emphasizes that qualitative surveys with open-ended questions provide detailed rather than brief, closed-ended data. All results gathered from this study will be analyzed and interpreted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presented the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender. The majority are male (64%) and females accounts for 36%. These statistics correspond to the data of the Philippine Council for Agriculture and Fisheries, as reported by the Philippine Information Agency (2022), indicating that women comprise only 41.7% of all registered agricultural workers and fisher folks. In the country, the agricultural labor force

remains a male-dominated sector. Arya et. Al (2020), indicated male farmers engage in more crop diversity practices and have greater decision making power. They also tend to possess more land and capital, as well as easier access to credit and education (Tenna et. al, 2017).

Table 1
Gender Distribution of the Respondents

Sex	f	Percentage
Male	16	64%
Female	9	36%
Total	25	100%

Table 2 highlighted the age distribution of the respondents, where majority fall within 41 to 50 years old (32%) and the least fall within 21-30 years old (8%). According to PhilAtlas (n.d), individuals aged 15-64 in Barangay Pal-ew are considered part of the economically active population and are potential members of the workforce. Additionally, based on the barangay's age dependency, there are 71 youth dependents for every 100 working age population plus 8 senior dependents making a total of 79 dependents for every 100 members of the working population.

Table 2
Age Distribution of the Respondents

Age	f	Percentage
21-30	2	8%
31-40	3	12%
41-50	8	32%
51-60	7	28%
61-70	5	20%
Total	25	100%

Table 3 presented the different challenges associated with farming, such as unpredictable weather conditions, which lead to difficulties in producing sufficient food supply for the nation. The Department of Agriculture reported agricultural losses of ₱8.1 billion and ₱14.25 billion due to typhoons in 2019 and 2020, respectively. Climate change has become a serious issue that impoverishes farmers, causing significant losses and damages, which result in financial constraints (Candano, 2025).

Moreover, another critical challenge faced by many farmers is their limited knowledge of farming techniques, market opportunities, and certification processes, all of which are crucial for their day-to-day operations. It is undeniable that most farmers from rural areas lack exposure to developments in organic agriculture, such as composting methods, pest control, and soil fertility management. These deficiencies hinder their ability to fully utilize organic farming practices (Arga & Labasan, 2025).

On the other hand, Daghigh (2019) cited financial instability as one of the most significant risk factors affecting farmers' mental health, alongside poor physical health. Based on the survey questionnaire, respondents also emphasized their lack of financial capacity to procure farming equipment and fertilizers. Similarly, Baffes and Temaj (2025) reported that fertilizer prices continued to rise in the second quarter of 2025, with the World Bank's fertilizer price index increasing by 15 percent since the beginning of the year.

Furthermore, given the wide array of challenges faced by the respondents, when asked how these challenges affected them psychologically, the majority emphasized experiencing stress, particularly because farming is their primary source of livelihood. Stress has been especially threatening for older individuals, leaving long-term effects that can damage health. There is a direct relationship between psychosocial stressors and disease, which is linked to the nature and persistence of these stressors as well as the body's vulnerability (Schneiderman et al., 2005).

Table 3.
Problems Associated to Farming

Type of Problem	f	Percentage
Unpredictable Weather	25	100%
Lack of Resources	20	80%
Financial Constraint	25	100%
Lack of Knowledge	21	84%
Stress	25	100%
Fatigue	22	88%

Conclusions

The study revealed that farmers face various challenges that affect their psychological well-being. Unpredictable weather conditions, financial constraints, limited access to farming equipment, and lack of knowledge were identified as significant factors influencing both farming productivity and mental health. These challenges shape the lived experiences of farmers and highlight the complex pressures inherent in agricultural work. Understanding these challenges is crucial for developing targeted interventions that address both practical and psychological needs of farmers. Moreover, recognizing their lived experiences can inform policy and community support programs.

Financial scarcity was found to directly impact farmers' mental health and overall quality of life. The inability to procure necessary resources, such as fertilizers and farming tools, not only reduces productivity but also increases stress, anxiety, and other psychological burdens. This economic strain often affects family livelihoods and creates uncertainty regarding future farming seasons, which can further exacerbate feelings of helplessness and frustration. Farmers must constantly balance immediate survival needs

with long-term planning, making financial challenges a persistent source of pressure. Economic difficulties, therefore, have both immediate and long-lasting effects on mental health and the ability to sustain productive farming practices.

Limited knowledge and exposure to modern farming practices further exacerbate these pressures. The lack of farming literacy reduces the ability to adapt to changing conditions, increasing feelings of helplessness and frustration. Providing farmers with access to training, education, and relevant information is essential for improving agricultural outcomes and supporting their psychological resilience. Overall, addressing these intertwined challenges can enhance both the quality of life for farmers and the sustainability of agricultural practices in the community.

Recommendations

The study presented the different struggles and challenges faced by farmers, affecting their day-to-day lives and psychological well-being. To address these challenges, the researchers emphasize the importance of providing comprehensive psychological and agricultural extension programs, as they equip farmers with the training, resources, and guidance needed to improve their knowledge and adopt modern and sustainable practices. By bridging the knowledge gap and offering practical support, these extension programs not only enhance agricultural productivity but also help reduce stress and strengthen farmers' psychological resilience.

In addition, these programs can foster a sense of community and mutual support among farmers, encouraging collaboration and the sharing of best practices. This social aspect can further alleviate feelings of isolation and helplessness, which are often associated with the pressures of farming. By combining practical agricultural training with psychological support, extension programs can address both the material and emotional needs of farmers, promoting long-term sustainability and well-being.

Ultimately, addressing the multifaceted challenges of farmers requires a holistic approach that considers both their economic and psychological needs. Implementing targeted interventions, providing continuous education, and ensuring access to adequate resources can significantly improve farmers' productivity while safeguarding their mental health. By prioritizing both the agricultural and psychological well-being of farmers, communities can cultivate a more resilient and sustainable farming sector for the future.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers ensured that all prescribed ethical standards were followed, observed, and implemented. Informed consent was obtained from the respondents, with assurance of their anonymity and the freedom to withdraw at any time. Data privacy was strictly observed, along with the confidentiality of all responses. The safety and well-being of the respondents were safeguarded throughout the duration of the study, and no conflict of interest was present. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and the interpretation of findings

was free from bias. AI tools were thoughtfully used to enhance grammar and maintain professionalism in the presentation of the text.

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